

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF WOVEN COMPOSITE

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1 Introduction

Plain weave fabrics are used as reinforcements in composites in order to obtain balanced ply properties and improved inter-laminar properties. These advantages are realized at the cost of reduced stiffness and strength in the in-plane directions. So, it is necessary to study the mechanical behavior of such composites in order to fully realize their potential.

Plain weave fabrics are formed by interlacing or weaving two sets of orthogonal tows. The tows in the longitudinal direction are known as warp tows. The tows in the transverse direction are known as the fill tows or weft. The interlacing causes bending in the tows, called tow crimp. Plain weave fabrics can be arranged in different laminate stacking configurations^[1]. A single lamina consists of warp and fill-tows surrounded by matrix in a single layer as shown in Fig.1. The iso-phase configuration consists of plain weave laminate arranged one above the other so that the undulations are in phase. The out-of-phase configuration consists of plain weave laminates arranged in a symmetric manner, so that the undulations are out of phase by a , which is the pitch of the undulation (Fig. 1). In order to model the single lamina, iso-phase, and out-of-phase laminates using finite element methods, only the representative volume elements (RVE) of the

respective configurations are considered. The RVE is the repeating element (unit cell) that represents the whole composite fabric structure (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 Schematic representation of fabric geometry

Numerous methods are available for modeling and analyzing plain weave fabric composites. There are two main categories: analytical models and numerical models. Chou and Ito^[2] developed 1-D analytical models of the plain weave laminated composites for determining their mechanical properties. The undulation of the fill tow was not considered for the analysis. Three different laminate stacking configurations were considered for the analysis: iso-phase, out-of-phase and random phase laminates. Mathematical models of the

configurations were explained very well and predictions of inplane modulus are compared to experiments for all three configurations. The undulation of warp tow was assumed to be sinusoidal and two types of cross-section were assumed for the fill tows: sinusoidal and elliptical. The iso-strain condition was used for evaluating the stiffness of the plain weave laminates.

Ishikawa and Chou^[3,4] developed three models to predict the elastic properties of woven fabric laminates. The mosaic model^[3] was used to predict the stiffness of satin weave fabric composites. The model neglects the tow crimp and idealizes the composite as an assemblage of asymmetric cross-ply laminates. Then, an iso-stress or iso-strain condition was used to predict the stiffness of the laminate depending on whether the laminates are assembled in series or parallel. Since the model neglects the tow crimp, the prediction of stiffness is not accurate. The fiber undulation model^[3] or the 1-D model considers fiber undulation in the longitudinal direction but neglects it in the transverse direction. The bridging model^[4], a combination of mosaic and fiber undulation model, was developed for satin weave fabrics. The model reduces to the crimp model^[3] for plain weave fabrics and hence the stiffness prediction is not accurate. In this studying, a straight edge model was designed trying to simply the analysis process.

2 Geometric modeling

2.1 Finite Element Modeling

The geometric model describing the internal geometry of the RVE of a single lamina is developed from measurements taken on photomicrographs of the faces of the representative volume element (RVE). From photomicrographs of the RVE faces, the bounds of the tow in the fill cross-section and warp cross-section were almost symmetry in plane.

The RVE consists of four intertwined tows surrounded by the matrix. There are four volumes depicting the tows. Two of them represent two half tows in the x-direction (warp tows) and the remaining two represent two half tows in the y-direction (fill tows). Each volume (tow) is modeled as a unidirectional composite with orthotropic properties in the material coordinate system that follows the tow undulation.

Fig. 2 Photomicrograph of the fill face of fabric

From the photomicrograph of the RVE faces, the curvature of the bounds of the tow is so small that we could substitute the curve boundary for a straight line, which will greatly simplify the complexity of the model of the unit cell, and retain precision of simulation result as well.

Fig. 3 3-D views of a plain weave fabric

The models were meshed using 20 node solid element of SOLID-95 in ANSYS^[5], as shown in Fig. 4. The material properties of the tows vary along the orientation of the path line.

The fiber volume fraction in the tow V_f is necessary to calculate the tow properties using micromechanics. Although the tow volume fraction is very difficult to measure directly, it can be

calculated from the overall volume fraction V_o and the calculated mesoscale volume fraction V_g . It was easily to calculate the fiber volume fraction in this model, which is 0.5.

Fig. 4 Finite element model of the weave fabric

2.2 Material Properties and Calculation of Elasticity Modulus

The material properties of the tows are calculated using micromechanics [6,7] with V_o as fiber volume fraction. The elastic properties of constituent materials (fiber and matrix) for the CERL fabric are obtained from [8] and for the remaining materials from [2]. The tows are transversely isotropic and thus require only five properties (E_1 , E_2 , G_{12} , m_{12} , m_{23}). Then, the properties are assigned to the tow and matrix elements in ANSYS. The next step is to apply the boundary conditions and analyze the results. Since AS4 carbon fiber is transversely isotropic, the elastic properties are calculated using periodic microstructure micromechanics for transversely isotropic fibers [7]. As an alternative [6] to while taking into account transversely isotropic fibers with a simple model [9], the following procedure is proposed. First, calculate E_1 using the warp fiber modulus E_{f1} and m_{12f} of the fiber, and the elastic properties of matrix. Next, calculate E_2 using the radial fiber modulus E_{f2} and m_{12f} of the fiber, and elastic properties of matrix. Then, calculate G_{12} using the value of G_{12f} , m_{12f} of the fiber and elastic properties of matrix. Finally, calculate G_{23} using E_{f2} , m_{23f} of the fiber and elastic properties of matrix, where m_{23f} is

calculated from the transversely isotropic conditions. These properties are checked for the restrictions on elastic constants [8]. The results are compared with [6] that assumes fibers to be transversely isotropic and with [6], that uses only longitudinal fiber properties E_{f1} and m_{12f} . The results obtained from the approximate procedure show good correlation with the micromechanics model for transversely isotropic fibers. The elastic properties of the constituent materials and the overall properties of the tow (composite) are reported in Table 1.

Table 1 Elastic properties of the fiber and matrix of RVE

	Fiber		Matrix
E_l longit.[GPa]	221	E_m [GPa]	3.4
E_t transv.[GPa]	16.6	ν	0.35
ν	0.26		

Fig. 5 Tensile deformation of finite element model

As shown in Fig.5, the Elasticity modulus in x-direction could be calculated by the loading a nonzero displacement on the face which is located at $X=l_w$. According to the periodic boundary condition, symmetrical boundary conditions were loaded on the faces which are located at $X=0$, $Y=0$ and $Z=0$. The nodes should be coupled together on faces which are located at $Y=H_z$ and $Z=l_z$ so that the deformation will be in the same pattern in the faces. The total reaction forces in x-direction on face located at $X=l_w$

could be obtained in the analysis result [10].

The elasticity modulus in x-direction could be calculated by the following equation-1.

$$E_x = \frac{\sum F_x \times l_w}{l_z \times H_z \times \Delta x}$$

The elasticity modulus in the other two directions could be calculated using the same method introduced previously.

3 Analysis Results

The elasticity modulus in x-direction and y-direction has been calculated in this studying respectively. The analysis results using FEM are listed in the following figures. Fig. 6 shows the deformation in x-direction, from which we can see that, the deformation is continuously distributed on every elements.

Fig. 6 Displacement nephogram of the whole model

Fig. 7 shows the stress in x-direction, from which we can see that, the fabric bundles mainly endured the tensile stress. This is because elasticity modulus of fabric bundle is higher than the matrix material. The calculated elasticity modulus in x-direction is 10 GPa, and in y-direction is 1.25Gpa, which are higher than matrix (3.4GPa) and lower than fabric (221GPa and 16.6GPa).

Fig. 7 Stress nephogram of the whole model

4 Conclusions

In this studying, the elasticity properties of plain weave fabrics using FEM. The geometric model was based on microphotograph measurements which were translated into a solid model and an FE model using commercial software. The elasticity values predicted by the FEM were thought to be reasonable for the weave fabrics. We want to prove the analysis results with experiment in the following research.

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